

Changing Irrigation Pattern In Hamirpur District: A Geographical Analysis

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Abstract

Irrigation is the process to supply water to crops by various methods such as pipes, canals, sprinklers, or other man-made means. Irrigation water brought from groundwater and surface water. Irrigation plays important role to grow crops on a consistent schedule, irrigation also creates more reliable food supplies. To help meet demand for food, more farmland and more irrigation may be needed. Climate change has increased more challenges to water supply for irrigation from both sources surface and groundwater, which will be affect to food security and crops production. in this paper an attempt has been made to analyse the spatio-temporal variations of irrigation pattern in development blocks level in Hamirpur district Uttar India, by taking average value during the periods between off from 1999-2003 to 2019-23. In this paper also has discussed the sources of irrigation in the district. Development blocks of the district are the unit of this study.

Keywords Irrigation, Crops Production, Productivities, Climate Change, Water Management.

Introduction

Irrigation is one of the major and initial tools to modernised agriculture. It plays the key role in terms of to increase crops production and productivities, increase farmer's income, food security and agriculture based industries. In India, agriculture is very important sector to the socio economic development, it contribute 17% of GDP and 54% of total workforce engaged in agriculture and allied sector activities (annual report 2022-23) employment and food security, thus facilities of irrigation in being very crucial for agriculture in India. Irrigation has historical evidence to be practice all over the world. Ancient civilizations in many parts of the world practiced irrigation to grow crops, there were many example could be seen in Inca, Mesopotamia and Nile river civilization.

In India, irrigation play significant role to make self-sufficient country in term of food production and requirement. The success of green revolution in India was the result of irrigation development in green revolution belt. Irrigation in India: Irrigation Projects in India are classified into three Categories; such as Major Irrigation projects have a more than 10,000 hectare Cultivable Command Area (CCA), Medium Irrigation Projects less than 10,000 hectare CCA but more than 2,000 hectare. Minor Irrigation projects 2,000 hectare or less (CCA).

Niti Aayog has reported 73.1 million hectares irrigated (52%) area in 2022-23 which was 56.9 million hectares in 2001-02. 'Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchayee Yojana' was launched in 2014 with the motto of 'Har Khet Ko Paani' to ensure access to some means of protective irrigation to all agricultural farms in the country, to produce 'per drop more crop', thus bringing much desired rural prosperity.

Objective of study

1. To analysis the temporal change in irrigation pattern in the blocks of district.
2. To find out the spatial variation of irrigation pattern at blocks level.
3. To suggest the crop pattern in the district.

Review of Literature There has been done lot of work on the irrigation and related to it sectors all over the world as well India. Kumar et al. (2023), studies the changing pattern of irrigation intensity in Haryana. In their studies they highlighted the significant change in the irrigation intensity due to government intervention such as PMSY and Har Khet Ko Pani.

In his study, S. Motebennur (2013) examined the spatial and temporal distribution of irrigation and impact of irrigation on agricultural development. His study found an improvement in the district's net irrigated area is helpful for the continued development of the agricultural sector. N. Umer (2020) has examined irrigation sources including tube well and canal irrigation in his research. In their study, Kamble et al. (2018) focused on the issue of different sources of irrigation intensity, including lift, well, and canal irrigation. Significant variations have been noted in the research area's canal irrigation intensity. The size and distribution of irrigated lands worldwide are still very unclear, despite their importance for food security and the global water cycle (smarty, 2002).

Methodology The study of this paper is based on secondary data which have been collected from the District Statistical Magazine, Economics and Statistics Division of Planning Department, U.P. Intensity of irrigation has been calculated using the formula of dividing the net irrigated area by the net cropped area in a given agricultural year and multiplying by hundred.

$$Irrigation\ intensity = \frac{Net\ Irrigated\ Area}{Net\ Shown\ Area} \times 100$$

Area of study

A brief study of the regional character is attempted in this paper which is useful for Considerate the basis for pattern of irrigation, sources of irrigation and numbers of its.

Hamirpur district lies between from 25°79' north Latitudes to 26°08' north latitudes and from 79°23' East Longitude to 80°21' East longitudes. Hamirpur is bounded by districts Jalaun, Kanpur and Fatehpur in north, Banda in east, Mahoba in south and Districts of Jhansi and Jalaun on the West. From south to north distance is 83 kilometres and from east to west distance is 94 kilometres. The district occupies an area of 4,121.9 km². The district has a population of 1,042,374 (2001 census). As of 2011 it is the third least populous district of Uttar Pradesh (out of 71), after Mahoba and Chitrakoot. Two major rivers Yamuna and Betwa meet here. On the banks of Betwa lies the "Coarse sand" which is exported to many parts in Uttar Pradesh. The Annual Average of rainfall of the study area is 638 mm according to metrological department of India (data are based on 1980-2010 rainfall data). Major resources of irrigation in Hamirpur district are canals, tank, wells, tube wells and pumps set.

Source; Administrative Atlas Census of India

The terrain of Hamirpur situated in the Peninsular Shield, is differentiated into a rocky surface of Bundelkhand highland and alluvium surface of Ganga Plain. The rocky surface, attaining elevations of 225 to 335m, contains pediment and dissected denudational hills. The Ganga Plain, with elevation of 110 to 250 m in the northern part, consists of upland and lowland. Banda Plain and Varanasi Plain constitute upland. Banda Plain is rolling with inselbergs and is sandy to gravelly, whereas Varanasi Plain is flat and salty in nature (Hamirpur NAQUIM report).

Result and Discussion

Irrigation sources in Hamirpur district major sources of irrigation in Hamirpur district were canals, tube wells, ground level pump sets, and Pakka well at that time of period, we can see into the (table 1). In 2002-03 there were 11 canals with the length of 832 km, 516 government tube wells, 2884 Pakka wells, 992 pump sets and total tube was recorded 11656 in the district. In 2022-23 there was no change in length of canals but rapidly change recorded in the numbers of total tube well the numbers (mainly private tube wells) increased from 11656 to 16639, ground level pump sets also increased from 993 to 2505 and Pakka well increased by 1000 unit in the district. If we looked in the blocks level during the given period there have been significant changes recorded in irrigation sources, but the changes were varies from one block to another's given in the (table 1).

Table1. Irrigation sources in the district during 2002-03 and 2022-23

Blocks	Length of canals(km)		State Tube Wells(No.)		Pakkaa Wells (No.)		Ground Level Pump Sets		Tube wells	
	2001-02	2021-22	2001-02	2021-22	2001-02	2021-22	2001-02	2021-22	2001-02	2021-22
Kurara	78	78	110	186	1	3	45	220	564	1373
Sumerpur	58	58	154	192	131	176	102	376	2130	2989
Sarila	73	73	116	145	148	199	83	269	1501	2251
Gohand	147	147	31	43	1515	2039	51	217	813	1488
Rath	116	116	0	2	268	360	167	434	3011	3641
Muskara	235	235	13	16	635	855	391	595	1390	1790
Modaha	125	125	72	102	186	250	153	394	2247	3107
District	832	832	516	686	2884	3882	992	2505	11656	16639

Source - District Statistical Magazine, Hamirpur District.

Table2. Percentage of irrigated area by different sources 2001-2002 (area in per cent)

Blocks	Canals	Tube wells				Pakka Wells	Others sources
		Govt. Wells	Tube	private wells	Tube		
Kurara	38.70	36.56		19.06	4.20	0.58	
Sumerpur	15.00	31.70		41.47	9.4	1.39	
Sarila	13.13	23.47		5.428	53.16	4.36	
Gohand	17.38	6.59		11.21	63.03	1.77	
Rath	43.65	1.00		4.83	45.89	4.1	
Muskara	53.41	2.66		32.94	4.76	5.25	
Modaha	20.10	9.18		44.98	8.32	16.30	
Total District	28.6	14.24		24.95	26.25	5.25	

Source - District Statistical Magazine, Hamirpur District.

Table3 Percentage of area irrigated by different sources 2021-22 (area in per cent)

Blocks	Canals	Tube wells		Pakka Wells	Others sources
		Govt. Tube Wells	private Tube wells		
Kurara	11.09	23.99	59.46	0.93	4.2
Sumerpur	3.99	16.35	77.10	0.11	2.37
Sarila	0.37	30.39	58.52	3.71	6.09
Gohand	11.3	3.45	64.49	14.6	6.02
Rath	29.73	0.14	57.78	8.40	3.86
Muskara	21.52	4.309	70.51	2.50	0.81
Modaha	5.34	10.35	81.851	0.48	0.83
Total District	11.9	11.77	69.88	3.21	2.73

Source - District Statistical Magazine, Hamirpur District.

Canals irrigation

Canals irrigation area was registered 28% out of total irrigated area in the district, in 2001-02. at the blocks level Muskara block recorded highest percentage of canal irrigating (53%) followed by Rath block (43%) and lowest area was recorded in Sarila blocks only (13%) under canal irrigation due to absence of canal facility. In 2021-22, canals irrigated area were registered 11.9% witch was decreased by 16 % in the given period of time. Rath block recorded 29.7% followed by Muskara block in this category. All blocks have recorded decrease under the canals irrigation category in this period.

Tube wells irrigation

There were two types of tube wells first was government tube wells second was private tube wells both were has largest proportion of irrigated area in the district . Tube wells irrigation has registered 38 % irrigated area which was the highest proportion of irrigation area in the district, in 2001-02. 24 % area was irrigated by the private tube wells and 14 % area was under the government tube wells irrigated area in the district. In 2021-22 area under the tube wells irrigation has increased by 42% and reached to 81% in district (table 2). It was highest proportion of irrigation source in district.

At the blocks level Sumerpur block recorded highest percentage irrigated area (73%) under the tube wells irrigation , followed by Kurara block (55%) and lowest area was recorded in Rath blocks only (6%) under the tube wells irrigation, in years 2001-02. The area under the tube wells has increased by 23% in Sumerpur and by 36% in Modaha block due to increase numbers of private tube wells in the blocks.

Pakka Wells' irrigation

Pakka wells' irrigation were major sources of irrigation in the district in year 2001-02, 26% area out of total irrigated area was irrigated by the wells in the district, it was the third largest sources of irrigation. In year 2021-22, this category has decreased only 3.2 % area irrigated under the pakka wells' irrigation system due to margin increased in number of wells (table1) in district.

Irrigation by other sources

In year 2001-02, 5.5% area was registered under the other sources of irrigation such as tank, pond and lakes in the district (table2). Modaha block recorded 16 % irrigated area under this category. 2.3% irrigated area registered under this category in year 2021-22 it has decreased by 3.2%.

Irrigation intensity and pattern in the district

Irrigation intensity has controlled by local climatology, geological structure, terrain, soil texture, physical conditions, technological advancement, innovation, human resources and level of socio economic development of any particular area. Agricultural pattern and degree of development of any region are mostly determined by the irrigation intensity and its system.

Intensity of irrigation in Hamirpur district has discussed in this paper at the development block wise. The intensity of irrigation of each block discusses following; (data show in the table no 4, 5 and 6).

Table 4 Irrigation Intensity during 2001-02

Blocks	Net sown area 2001-02 (in hectares.)	Net irrigated area 2001-02 (in hectares.)	Irrigation intensity
Kurara	31689	9090	28
Sumerpur	49758	16191	32
Sarila	46643	8206	17
Gohand	40889	16387	40
Rath	30517	16738	54
Muskara	40557	15687	38
Modaha	64150	16580	25

Table 5 Irrigation Intensity During 2021-22

Blocks	Net sown area 2021-22 (in hectares.)	Net irrigated area 2021-22 (in hectares.)	Irrigation intensity
Kurara	30031	22619	75
Sumerpur	47350	40695	85
Sarila	41752	16467	39
Gohand	40627	19647	48
Rath	30295	25143	82
Muskara	39109	37030	94
Modaha	54883	41005	74

Source - district statistical magazine, Hamirpur district.

Table 6 Changing Pattern of Irrigation Intensity From 2001-02 to 2021-22

Blocks	Irrigation Intensity 2001-02	Irrigation Intensity 2021-22	Change in Irrigation Intensity from 2001-02 to 2021-22
Kurara	28	75	47
Sumerpur	32	85	53
Sarila	17	39	22
Gohand	40	48	8
Rath	54	82	28
Muskara	38	94	56
Modaha	25	74	49

Source- based on Author's Calculation

Kurara Block

In 2001-02, Net irrigated area was reported 9090 hectares and Net sown area was 31689 hectares in the block. At this time irrigation intensity was observed 28% in the block. The intensity of irrigation was increased by 47% in 2021-2022 and reached 75%, and 22619 hectares Net irrigated area was reported out of net sown area 30031 hectares.

Sumerpur Block

In 2001-02, 16191 hectare area was reported net irrigated out of Net sown area 49758 hectare. At this irrigation intensity was observed 32% in the block. The intensity of irrigation was increased by 85% in 2021–202, and 40695 hectares Net irrigated area was reported out of net sown area 47350 hectares. There has been a 53% rise in irrigation intensity for under the evaluation period.

Sarila Block

Net sown area was reported 46643 hectares and 8206 hectares area was observed as net irrigated out of it, in 2001-02. At this period irrigation intensity was observed 17% in the block. In 2021–2022, Net irrigated area was reported 16467 hectares out of net sown area (41752 hectares). During the evaluation periods, the intensity of irrigation was hiked by 22% and increased to 39% in the block.

Gohand Block

Gohand block had reported Net sown area 40889 hectare and 16387 hectares net irrigated out of it in 2001-02, and irrigation intensity was observed 40% in the block. The intensity of irrigation was jumped by 8 % in 2021–2022 and reached to 48 %, and 19647 hectares Net irrigated area was reported out of net sown area 40627 hectares.

Rath Block

Rath block was registered 16738 hectares area as net irrigated out of 30517 hectares of Net sown area and irrigation intensity was observed 54 % in the block, in 2001-02. During the stud period of time, the intensity of irrigation was hiked by 28% and reached to 82 %; the Net irrigated area was reported 25143 hectares out of 30295 hectares of net sown area, in 2021–2022.

Muskara Block

In 2001-02, Muskara block has reported net irrigated area 15687 hectares out of Net sown area 40557 hectares. At this period, irrigation intensity was observed 38 percent in the block. During the evaluation period intensity of irrigation was increased by 56 % in 2021–2022 and reached to 94% due to numbers of private tube wells has rapidly increased in the block , and 37030 hectares Net irrigated area was reported out of net sown area 39109 hectares.

Modaha Block

In 2001-02, Modaha block net irrigated area has reported 16580 hectares out of Net sown area 64150 hectares. Irrigation intensity was observed 25% in the same period in the block. The intensity of irrigation was increased by 49% in 2021–2022 and reached 74%, and 41005 hectares Net irrigated area was reported out of net sown area 54883 hectares in the block.

Graph 1

Conclusion

There were recorded significance changes in the means of irrigation in last 20 years in Hamirpur district. Private tube wells and Pakka wells have increased in the district, while no change has been observed in the length of canals. During this period it has been observed that the net irrigated area has increased. To increase in cumulative agricultural area that has been observed mainly in the form of ground water.

All the blocks of Hamirpur district are rallied on ground water for irrigation. More than 50% of the irrigation system in all the blocks is ground water irrigation system, which is being used through tube wells, Pakka wells and wells.

To meet the demand of water for irrigation and to avoid the adverse impact of climate change, emphasis should be laid on the development of surface water sources for overall agricultural development, while ground water use should be minimized immediately. Management of irrigation is facing increasing difficulties due to water constraint and climate change. Crop yields are reduced and water consumption is increased due to climate change.

Under the Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchai Yojana, there is a need for construction of surface water sources in the district, so that in future, to meet demand of water for irrigation should be supplied from surface water sources and dependence on underground water irrigation system should be minimized. There is a need to expand the blocks in the Khet Talab Scheme district, run by the Government of Uttar Pradesh, and should be implemented effectively.

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